

Coarse-Grained Fundamental Forms for Characterizing Isometries of Trapezoid-based Origami Metamaterials

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1 Coarse-Grained Fundamental Forms for Characterizing Isometries of Trapezoid-based 2 Origami Metamaterials

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Investigations of origami tessellations as effective media reveal the ability to program the components of their elasticity tensor. However, existing efforts focus on crease patterns that are composed of parallelogram faces where the parallel lines constrain the quasi-static elastic response. In this work, crease patterns composed of more general trapezoid faces are considered and their low-energy linear response is explored. Deformations of such origami tessellations are modeled as linear isometries that do not stretch individual panels at the small scale yet map to non-isometric changes of coarse-grained fundamental forms that quantify how the effective medium strains and curves at the large scale. Two distinct mode shapes, a rigid breathing mode and a nonrigid shearing mode, are identified in the continuum model. A specific example, called Morph-derivative trapezoid-based origami, is presented with analytical expressions for its deformations in both the discrete and continuous models. A developable specimen is fabricated and tested to validate the analytical predictions. This work advances the continuum modeling of origami tessellations as effective media with the incorporation of more generic faces and ground states, thereby enabling the investigation of novel designs and applications.

13 INTRODUCTION

14 Origami sheets are two-dimensional surfaces with pre-
15 defined creases that control their three-dimensional re-
16 sponse to mechanical loads [1–4]. The fundamental prin-
17 ciple behind the behavior of origami is the difference be-
18 tween the energy scales of elastic deformations that bend
19 the panels (cubic in sheet thickness) and elastic deforma-
20 tions that stretch the panels (linear in sheet thickness).
21 This scaling leads to a quasi-static, low-energy response
22 dominated by the deformations that do not stretch the
23 panels, which we refer to as *linear isometries*. Since
24 this principle relies solely on the thickness of the sheet,
25 the linear isometries corresponding to a particular crease
26 pattern are largely material independent and therefore
27 realizable in both metallic [5–9] and polymeric [10–12]
28 materials over a range of length scales. Hence, an un-
29 derstanding of the origami kinematics tends to be more
30 consequential than an understanding of the origami dy-
31 namics for the design of origami metamaterials. There
32 are two specific applications of origami kinematics that
33 motivate our work.

34 The first application of interest is the class of isome-
35 tries referred to as *rigid folding mechanisms* that fold

36 the origami sheet along its predefined creases while keep-
37 ing the panels entirely rigid (no stretching or bending).
38 These rigid folding mechanisms are useful for the deploy-
39 ment and transformation of structures found in various
40 engineering applications including solar arrays [13, 14],
41 heart stents [15], and temporary shelters [16]. How-
42 ever, arbitrary quadrilateral-mesh crease patterns are not
43 rigidly foldable and a significant body of work is de-
44 voted towards the development of design principles [17–
45 22]. Moreover, arbitrary loads can lead to heterogeneous
46 actuation of the mechanism [23, 24] as well as undesirable
47 deformations due to the existence of isometries distinct
48 from the rigid folding mechanism [25] or the intersec-
49 tion of separate branches in the configuration space [26].
50 Therefore, efficient models for the response to external
51 loads can inform the methods for deployment and trans-
52 formation of origami structures along the programmed
53 rigid mechanism without exciting undesirable responses
54 via alternative low-energy instabilities.

55 The second application of interest is the continuum ap-
56 proximation (i.e., homogenization or coarse-graining) of
57 linear isometries in periodic origami tessellations. Such
58 approximations are valuable for both surface fitting [27]
59 and effective elasticity models [28–30], where deforma-
60 tions that do not stretch the individual panels generate
61 apparently non-isometric deformations at the large scale.
62 The main example in the existing literature is the class of

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63 parallelogram-based origami sheets, such as the Miura-
 64 ori crease pattern [31, 32]. An origami tessellation in
 65 this class is quasi-planar, in that its two primitive lat-
 66 tice vectors always lie in the same two-dimensional plane,
 67 and exhibits one rigid folding mechanism that changes its
 68 lattice vectors. Simultaneously, such a tessellation also
 69 exhibits two nonrigid linear isometries that bend the pan-
 70 els in addition to folding the creases. Approximating the
 71 origami tessellation as a continuous sheet reveals that the
 72 rigid isometry generates in-plane strain, the first non-
 73 rigid isometry generates out-of-plane curvature, and the
 74 second nonrigid isometry generates out-of-plane twist-
 75 ing [31–36]. These three modes function as a basis for
 76 more general low-energy deformations in effect contin-
 77 uum models [29, 30]. Moreover, analytical calculations
 78 show the crease geometry necessarily pairs a hydrostatic
 79 (dilation) strain mode with an anticlastic (saddle) cur-
 80 vature mode and a deviatoric (pure shear) strain mode
 81 with a synclastic (dome) curvature mode [31–36].

82 Our work seeks to expand the investigation of
 83 parallelogram-based origami sheets to more generic tes-
 84 sellations which possess two crucial differences from those
 85 composed of parallelograms [37, 38]. The first differ-
 86 ence is that a generic tessellation is quasi-cylindrical,
 87 rather than quasi-planar, in that its two primitive lat-
 88 tice vectors rotate about a common axis from cell to cell.
 89 The second difference is that such a quasi-cylindrical tes-
 90 sellation exhibits two linear isometries (rather than the
 91 one rigid and two non-rigid isometries discussed in the
 92 previous paragraph) that retain the quasi-cylindrical ge-
 93 ometry while changing its radius, height, and symme-
 94 try axis. We investigate these two linear isometries in
 95 rigidly-foldable trapezoid-based origami (TBO) tessella-
 96 tions, for which the constituent trapezoid faces have one
 97 less symmetry than the previously investigated parallel-
 98 ogram faces, to exemplify continuum approximations for
 99 the linear isometries in quasi-cylindrical origami tessella-
 100 tions. We show exemplar TBO folded from cardstock
 101 in their ground state configurations in Figs. 1(A-D)(i)
 102 and in rigidly folded configurations in Figs. 1(A-D)(ii).
 103 While such rigid folding mechanisms of TBO are identi-
 104 fied for select geometries, such as the arc pattern, in pre-
 105 vious works [39, 40], our work also identifies and models
 106 the nonrigid isometries shown in Figs. 1(A-D)(iii). Our
 107 theoretical model has two components. The first com-
 108 ponent determines and solves the compatibility condi-
 109 tions for the linear isometries within a single cell, which
 110 we show can be represented using the compatibility dia-
 111 grams shown in Figs. 1(A-D)(iv) where the meaning of
 112 the line styles and colors is explained in Supplemental
 113 Appendix, TBO Examples. The second component maps
 114 these linear isometries to their continuum approximation,
 115 which decomposes into one rigid breathing mode and one
 116 nonrigid shearing mode. We showcase our analytical re-
 117 sults for a class of origami crease patterns derived from
 118 the geometry presented in Ref. [34] that we refer to as the
 119 Morph-derivative TBO and perform laboratory scale ex-
 120 periments on a specimen manufactured from polypropy-

lene.

122 RESULTS

123 Periodic origami tessellations with generic faces adopt
 124 quasi-cylindrical ground states generated by the two
 125 primitive lattice vectors ($\ell_{1,2}$) and the two primitive lat-
 126 tice rotation matrices ($\mathbf{S}_{1,2}$) (see Fig. 2A). As shown in
 127 Refs. [37, 38], the lattice rotations share a common axis
 128 (\hat{S}) about which local frames are rotated by the respec-
 129 tive lattice rotation angle ($\eta_{1,2}$) (see Supplemental Ap-
 130 pendix, Lattice Compatibility for further details). Fur-
 131 thermore, the lattice vector components orthogonal to
 132 \hat{S} define a unique radius of curvature (R). Thus, we
 133 coarse-grain the lattice-scale geometry by taking the dis-
 134 crete cell indices (n_1, n_2) to the continuous surface co-
 135 ordinates (φ, z) (see Methods, Coarse-Graining) and ap-
 136 proximate the cylindrical ground state via the embedding
 137 $\mathbf{X}(\varphi, z) = R \cos \varphi \hat{x} + R \sin \varphi \hat{y} + z \hat{z}$. From the embedding,
 138 we compute the tangent vectors $\mathbf{t}_\mu \equiv \partial_\mu \mathbf{X}$ (using sub-
 139 scripts μ, ν to denote the surface coordinates) and the
 140 normal vector $\hat{n} \equiv \mathbf{t}_\varphi \times \mathbf{t}_z / |\mathbf{t}_\varphi \times \mathbf{t}_z|$ to construct the first
 141 fundamental form $I_{\mu\nu} \equiv \mathbf{t}_\mu \cdot \mathbf{t}_\nu$, the second fundamental
 142 form $II_{\mu\nu} \equiv \hat{n} \cdot \partial_\mu \mathbf{t}_\nu$, and the shape operator $\mathcal{S} \equiv \mathbf{II}^{-1}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{I} &= \begin{pmatrix} R^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{II} &= \begin{pmatrix} -R & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \mathcal{S} &= \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{R} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

143 The shape operator has eigenvalues equal to the princi-
 144 pal curvatures ($\kappa_1 = -1/R, \kappa_2 = 0$), eigenvectors equal
 145 to the principal directions ($\hat{v}_1 = (1, 0), \hat{v}_2 = (0, 1)$), de-
 146 terminant equal to the Gaussian curvature ($K = 0$), and
 147 trace equal to twice the mean curvature ($2H = -1/R$).

148 As shown in Refs. [37, 38], at the lattice-scale, these
 149 origami sheets generically exhibit two linear isometries
 150 under periodic boundary conditions which change the
 151 lattice vectors ($\ell_{1,2} \rightarrow \ell_{1,2} + \Delta_{1,2}$) and the lattice ro-
 152 tation matrices ($\mathbf{S}_{1,2} \rightarrow (\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{L}_{1,2})\mathbf{S}_{1,2}$), thereby induc-
 153 ing changes in the radius ($R \rightarrow R + \delta R$) and the rota-
 154 tion axis ($\hat{S} \rightarrow \hat{S} + \delta \hat{S}$) while preserving the cylindri-
 155 cal character to first order (see Supplemental Appendix,
 156 Lattice Compatibility). We write the generic deforma-
 157 tion $\mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{X} + \delta \mathbf{X}$ in terms of the vector field $\delta \mathbf{X} =$
 158 $\delta X_n (\cos \varphi \hat{x} + \sin \varphi \hat{y}) + \delta X_\varphi (-\sin \varphi \hat{x} + \cos \varphi \hat{y}) + \delta X_z \hat{z}$
 159 and determine the changes in the radial direction (δX_n),
 160 the azimuthal direction (δX_φ), and the axial direction
 161 (δX_z) that are mutually consistent with cylindrical defor-
 162 mations below (see Supplemental Appendix, Continuum
 163 Deformations).

164 Since cylinders have zero Gaussian curvature, the de-
 165 formation must satisfy $\delta K = 0$. The in-plane strain

FIG. 1. Examples of trapezoid-based origami folded from cardstock (i) quasi-cylindrical ground states, (ii) rigid folding cylindrical isometry (iii) non-rigid shear isometry, and (iv) diagrammatic representation of compatibility conditions with line styles signifying the coupling between amplitudes on the adjoined vertices and triangles indicating periodic directions (see Supplemental Appendix, Example TBO for more details). (A) Cylindrical geometry from Miura-derivative. (B) Extension of the pattern in panel A exhibiting a locked configuration. (C) Archimedean spiral from a graded Miura-derivative pattern. (D) Lemniscate of Bernoulli from a graded Miura-derivative with a parallelogram interface.

FIG. 2. Coarse-grained geometry. (A) Angled view of a quasi-cylindrical trapezoid-based origami tessellation with lattice vectors $\ell_{1,2}$, lattice rotation axis \hat{S} , and characteristic height h . (B) Top-down view of the tessellation shown in panel A with lattice rotation angle η_1 , radius R , and azimuthal surface coordinate φ . Continuum illustration of the (C) breathing mode and (D) shearing mode induced by the linear isometries of the tessellation shown in panel A.

166 along the azimuthal and axial directions take arbitrary, but spatially constant, values ($\delta I_{\varphi\varphi} = \varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi}$ and
 167 $\delta I_{zz} = \varepsilon_{zz}$) because they are unconstrained by the cylindrical character of the deformation. Lastly, we consider
 168 a generic deformation as a linear combination of a breathing mode that changes the first principal curvature
 169 ($\delta\kappa_1 = -\delta R/R^2$) without changing the principal directions ($\delta\hat{v}_1 = (0,0)$, $\delta\hat{v}_2 = (0,0)$) and a shearing
 170 mode that changes the principal directions ($\delta\hat{v}_1 = (0, \sigma_1)$, $\delta\hat{v}_2 = (\sigma_2, 0)$) without changing the first principal curvature
 171 ($\delta\kappa_1 = 0$). Such modes are the only two homogeneous deformations that maintain the cylindrical character
 172 (see Supplemental Appendix, Continuum Deformations). Here, $\varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi}$, ε_{zz} , δR , σ_1 , and σ_2 all depend implicitly
 173 on the geometry of the underlying crease pattern, and this relationship constitutes the basis of the origami
 174 sheets as mechanical metamaterials. We find that the breathing mode (illustrated in Fig. 2C) is quantified by
 175 $\delta X_n = \delta R$, $\delta X_\varphi = (\varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi}/(2R) - \delta R)\varphi$, and $\delta X_z = \varepsilon_{zz}z/2$.
 176 The corresponding changes to the fundamental forms are

186 written:

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\mathbf{I} &= \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi} & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_{zz} \end{pmatrix}, \\ \delta\mathbf{II} &= \begin{pmatrix} \delta R - \frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi}}{R} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \delta\mathbf{S} &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\delta R}{R^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

187 We find that the shearing mode (illustrated in Fig. 2D)
 188 is quantified by $\delta X_n = 0$, $\delta X_\varphi = \varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi}\varphi/(2R) + \sigma_1 R z$, and
 189 $\delta X_z = \varepsilon_{zz}z/2 + \sigma_2\varphi$. The corresponding changes to the
 190 fundamental forms are written:

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\mathbf{I} &= \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi} & R^2\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 \\ R^2\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 & \varepsilon_{zz} \end{pmatrix}, \\ \delta\mathbf{II} &= -\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi}}{R} & R\sigma_1 \\ R\sigma_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \delta\mathbf{S} &= \frac{1}{R} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma_2 \\ -\sigma_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix},\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

191 Our work focuses on applying the above analysis to the
 192 particular case of rigidly foldable TBO, including all of
 193 the crease patterns shown in Figs. 1(A-D)(i) and, more
 194 generically, crease patterns for which the parallel edges
 195 of the trapezoidal faces ensure $\ell_1 \perp \hat{S}$ and $\ell_2 \parallel \hat{S}$ along
 196 the rigid folding configuration manifold. For the crease
 197 pattern in Fig. 1(A)(i), the orientation of the lattice vectors
 198 is because the subsequent parallel edges rotate the faces by
 199 complementary dihedral angles so that there is no net rotation,
 200 similar to the reason a parallelogram-based origami sheet stays
 201 planar. However, for the crease pattern in Fig. 1(B), the
 202 dihedral angles are not complementary but still sum to 2π .
 203 The consequence is that the rigid folding mechanism (demonstrated
 204 in Figs. 1(A-D)(ii)) is characterized by the breathing mode
 205 of Eqn. (2), and, by process of elimination, the remaining
 206 isometry (demonstrated in Figs. 1(A-D)(iii)) is characterized
 207 by the shearing mode of Eqn. (3). Interestingly, the crease
 208 patterns shown in Figs. 1(C,D) exhibit similar behavior despite
 209 having spatially varying crease patterns, and hence spatially
 210 varying radii, that only repeat along the rotation axis.

211 We provide more clarity on these modes by developing
 212 unit cell compatibility conditions for the class of TBO
 213 with parallel edges that alternate in length. Rather than
 214 triangulating the crease pattern as frequently done in
 215 previous works [31–35], we separately consider folding
 216 degrees of freedom on the vertices, denoted by the *vertex*
 217 *amplitudes* \mathcal{V} , and bending degrees of freedom on the faces,
 218 denoted by the *face amplitudes* \mathcal{F} (see Methods, Linear
 219 Isometry Model) as introduced in Ref. [36] for the special
 220 case of parallelogram-based origami. The amplitude on a
 221 vertex maps to changes in the dihedral angles, which are
 222 not required to be uniform along the edge unless the isometry
 223 is rigid. Instead, a gradient

in the folding along a crease generates bending of the adjacent faces, as quantified by the respective face amplitudes. For this reason, constraints on the face amplitudes can be integrated out, thereby yielding compatibility conditions that map from vertex amplitudes to vertex constraints which we illustrate via the compatibility diagrams shown in Figs. 1(A-D)(iv). Here, each node is assigned a vertex amplitude and the line style of the edges indicate coupling coefficients that depend on the crease geometry (see Supplemental Appendix, TBO Examples). When the coupling coefficients are uniform along the edges, such as in Fig. 1(A)(iv), the rigid mode ($\mathcal{F} = 0$ for all faces) is represented by uniform assignment of vertex amplitudes ($\mathcal{V} = 1$ for all vertices). In contrast, when the coupling coefficients are nonuniform along the edges, such as in Fig. 1(B)(iv), the vertex amplitudes of the rigid mode are proportional to one another to ensure the folding is uniform along the creases. In either case, we find that this family of TBO *always* exhibits a nonrigid mode represented by uniform face amplitudes ($\mathcal{F} = 1$ for all faces) and zero vertex amplitudes ($\mathcal{V} = 0$ for all vertices). Since the breathing (shearing) mode is generated by the rigid (nonrigid) isometry, its modal stiffness depends entirely on the stiffness of the creases (faces). This representation of the isometries effectively integrates the three-dimensional geometry out of the analysis to enable a succinct analytical classification of the modes.

Analysis of Morph-derivative Trapezoid-based Origami

We consider the family of Morph-derivative TBO, such as the example shown in Fig. 3(A). Similar to the family of Morph parallelogram-based origami introduced in Ref. [34], the unit cell of these periodic crease patterns is constructed from copies of a base vertex that is parameterized by the two independently chosen sector angles α and β . The three remaining vertices of the cell have identical or supplementary ($\alpha' \equiv \pi - \alpha$, $\beta' \equiv \pi - \beta$) sector angles and the distinction in the present work is that the vertices are arranged to form trapezoid faces rather than parallelograms. We exclusively consider isosceles trapezoids to simplify analytic expressions, but our model applies to tessellations composed of more general trapezoids and with larger unit cells. Thus, each of the trapezoids has two legs of length q , one base of length p , and one base of either $s_\alpha \equiv p - 2q \cos \alpha$ or $s_\beta \equiv p + 2q \cos \beta$ (see Fig. 3(B)). This yields the three-dimensional design space $(\alpha, \beta, q/p)$ for Morph-derivative TBO, where the magnitude of p dictates the scale of the system which has no role in our kinematic analysis.

Such a crease pattern has a rigid folding mechanism that we parameterize via the dihedral angle γ from which the remaining dihedral angles shown in Fig. 3(C) (θ , $\theta'' \equiv 2\pi - \theta$, ψ , and $\psi'' \equiv 2\pi - \psi$) are determined. The configuration manifold for a geometry with N_1 cells in the azimuthal direction is bounded by the closure condition

of the faces $\gamma = \pi$ shown in Fig. 3(F) and the closure condition of the cylinder $\eta N_1 = 2\pi$ shown in Fig. 3(H). We find these conditions restrict the space of viable configurations and system sizes, but we do not provide a thorough exploration of the design space in this work. We write the explicit expressions for the geometry along the rigid folding mechanism in Methods, Morph-derivative TBO Geometry. We compute the coarse-grained fundamental forms for a generic ground state then we use the mean curvature to determine the radius and the Jacobian to determine the characteristic height:

$$R = \frac{1}{4} (p + s_\beta + (p + s_\alpha) \cos \frac{\eta}{2}) \csc \frac{\eta}{2}, \quad (4)$$

$$h = 2q \sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma \csc \frac{\eta}{2}. \quad (5)$$

We find the components of the fundamental forms exactly match those shown in Eqn. (1). We show the radius as a function of the height along the configuration manifold in Fig. 3(E), and use the inset to highlight a change in slope after the cylinder reaches its maximum height as shown in Fig. 3(G). Since we have explicit formulae for the radius and the height, it is straightforward to expand the fundamental forms about infinitesimal changes to the dihedral angle γ along the rigid mechanism (see Supplemental Appendix, Morph-derivative Isometries). However, we utilize our framework for the rigid isometry to compare it with existing methods.

We first construct the compatibility diagram shown in Fig. 3(D) to determine the amplitude representation for the rigid isometry. Since there are three unique dihedral angles, we define the three folding coefficients $\zeta \equiv \sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma$, $\xi \equiv \sin \alpha^2 \sin \theta$, and $\chi \equiv \sin \beta^2 \sin \psi$ to quantify the respective changes in the dihedral angles $\delta\gamma$, $-\delta\psi$, and $-\delta\theta$. We see each edge of the diagram has a single color, and therefore conclude the rigid isometry of the mode is represented by the vertex amplitudes $\mathcal{V}^a = \mathcal{V}^b = \mathcal{V}^c = \mathcal{V}^d = 1$ and the face amplitudes $\mathcal{F}^A = \mathcal{F}^B = \mathcal{F}^C = \mathcal{F}^D = 0$. We integrate the changes in the lattice vectors and the lattice rotation matrices, then average according to our coarse-graining procedure to find:

$$\delta R = \frac{\zeta^2}{4} \left(p + s_\alpha + (p + s_\beta) \cos \frac{\eta}{2} \right) \csc^3 \frac{\eta}{2}, \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi} = \zeta^2 \csc \eta R \left(4R \sin \frac{\eta}{4} + (p + s_\alpha) \cos \frac{\eta}{2} \right), \quad (7)$$

$$\varepsilon_{zz} = 2 \sin \alpha \sin \beta \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \cos \frac{\psi}{2}, \quad (8)$$

where we determine $\varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi}$ and ε_{zz} directly from $\delta I_{\varphi\varphi}$ and δI_{zz} , respectively. These results are self-consistent with the continuum model which equates $\delta II_{\varphi\varphi} = \delta R - \varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi}/R$ and $\delta S_{\varphi\varphi} = \delta R/R^2$, and we obtain them using a slight adjustment to the averaging step of our coarse-graining procedure (see Supplemental Appendix, Morph-derivative Isometries). However, the Jacobian relating

FIG. 3. Morph-derivative trapezoid-based origami. (A) Perspective view of an example configuration with $N_1 = 4$ cells in the azimuthal direction and $N_2 = 4$ cells in the axial direction. (B) Primitive cell with vertices labeled $a, b, c,$ and d , faces labeled $A, B, C,$ and D , and edge lengths labeled $p = 1, q = 0.7, s_\alpha,$ and s_β . (C) Sector angles labeled $\alpha = 1.1, \alpha' \equiv \pi - \alpha, \beta = 2.1, \beta' \equiv \pi - \beta$ and dihedral angles labeled $\gamma, \psi, \psi' \equiv 2\pi - \psi,$ and $\theta, \theta' \equiv 2\pi - \theta$. (D) Compatibility diagram for vertex amplitudes with edges representing the coupling coefficients based on the folding coefficients $\zeta, \xi,$ and χ . (E) Nonlinear evolution of the height and radius of the crease pattern shown in panel A along the rigid folding mode, with the flat folded state shown in panel F, maximal height state shown in panel G, and closed state shown in panel H. (F-H) Front and top-down views of states labeled in panels E, I. (I) Linear response along the configuration manifold as a function of the dihedral angle, γ , quantified by the pitch p induced by the non-rigid mode and the ratio dh/dR of the rigid mode.

325 the discrete lattice coordinates to the continuous surface
 326 coordinates plays an important role here: the terms enter-
 327 ing the fundamental forms in Eqn. (2) are not given
 328 by the partial derivative of those in Eqn. (1) with respect
 329 to the dihedral angle that functions as the configuration
 330 parameter. Instead, the strains arise from the deriva-
 331 tives of the Jacobian which highlights the way the lattice
 332 geometry gives rise to the effective behavior of the mate-
 333 rial. The axial strain ε_{zz} maps to changes in the height
 334 $\delta h = h\varepsilon_{zz}/2$ of the cylinder whereas the azimuthal strain
 335 $\varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi}$ opens or closes the cylinder without changing its cur-
 336 vature, which instead are characterized by δR . We con-

337 sider the ratio $\delta h/\delta R$ analogously to the Poisson's ratio
 338 but instead characterizing the relative amount of axial
 339 stretching and radial dilation. We see from our expres-
 340 sions in Eqns. (6, 8) that when one of the dihedral angles
 341 (ψ or θ) changes its mountain/valley assignment this ra-
 342 tio changes signs, which is the same observation made for
 343 the Poisson's ratio in parallelogram-based origami. This
 344 further illustrates the functionality of Morph-derivative
 345 TBO as a transformable mechanical metamaterial.

346 We repeat this analysis for the nonrigid isometry which
 347 we cannot describe in terms of changes to the dihedral
 348 angles exclusively. Since this crease pattern falls within

the broader set of TBO that our theory applies to, the nonrigid isometry is represented by the vertex amplitudes $\mathcal{V}^a = \mathcal{V}^b = \mathcal{V}^c = \mathcal{V}^d = 0$ and the face amplitudes $\mathcal{F}^A = \mathcal{F}^B = \mathcal{F}^C = \mathcal{F}^D = 1$. We again integrate the changes in the lattice vectors and the lattice rotation matrices, then average according to our coarse-graining procedure to find:

$$\sigma_1 = 1, \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_2 = -R^2 - \frac{1}{4}(p^2 + s_\alpha s_\beta) \tan \frac{\eta}{2} \csc \frac{\eta}{2}, \quad (10)$$

where we determine σ_1 and σ_2 directly from $\mathcal{S}_{z\varphi} = \sigma_1/R$ and $\mathcal{S}_{\varphi z} = \sigma_2/R$ and find that the diagonal components of the strain vanish: $\varepsilon_{\varphi\varphi} = \varepsilon_{zz} = 0$. We confirm these quantities are self consistent with $\delta I_{\varphi z} = \delta I_{z\varphi} = R^2\sigma_1 + \sigma_2$, $\delta II_{\varphi z} = \delta II_{z\varphi} = R\sigma_1$ without any adjustment to the averaging step of our coarse-graining procedure. Here, there is an apparent discrepancy regarding the units of σ_1 and σ_2 : from dimensional analysis of Eqn. (3), σ_1 must have units of inverse area and σ_2 must be dimensionless. However, our calculations leading to Eqns. (9, 10) use a dimensionless face amplitude to simplify our calculations while the integration framework assumes the face amplitude has units of inverse length. This is in contrast to the vertex amplitudes which are always dimensionless. Introducing such a length scale, for example from the square root of the cell area, resolves the apparent discrepancy. The self consistency of our results relies on both the averaging process in our coarse-graining method and the inclusion of the Jacobian to transform from the discrete lattice coordinates to the continuous surface coordinates. While for the nonrigid isometries of parallelogram-based origami the averaging is also important, the Jacobian may be neglected because the ground states are quasi-periodic.

Experiments of Miura-derivative Trapezoid-based Origami

We fabricate and test an example Morph-derivative TBO crease pattern (see Methods, Fabrication and Testing). We select a developable pattern ($\beta = \pi - \alpha$) so that we can construct the crease pattern from a monolithic sheet (see Fig. 4(A)) rather than the assembly of individual panels, such as done in Ref. [41]. For this reason, we refer to this family of crease patterns as Miura-derivative TBO, whereas it is called the arc pattern in previous work [39, 40]. Since the sector angles are not independently chosen, these crease patterns have a two-dimensional design space parameterized by $(\alpha, q/p)$ with the geometry indicated in Figs. 4(B,C,E) and the compatibility diagram illustrated on the cell geometry in Fig. 4(D). After fabrication, the creases undergo plastic deformation and adopt the quasi-cylindrical ground state shown in Fig. 4(F); the tessellation tends to return to this particular configuration after any deformation.

We perform a quantitative test of the nonlinear rigid isometry and a qualitative test of the linear nonrigid isometry. For the rigid isometry, we focus on the relationship between the height and radius then compare with our analytical theory. Rather than averaging over the vertices, which could lead to the accumulation of systematic error, we measure the radii of the innermost (R_i) and outermost (R_e) components of the cross section. We show the experimentally measured values and the analytical predictions in Fig. 4(G), along with images of the exact configurations measured in Fig. 5. We see good agreement between the measurements and predictions until the tessellation becomes fairly flattened at configuration 8. We attribute this discrepancy, which becomes more pronounced as the tessellation flattens further, to systematic error arising from the large angle subtended by the radial measurement. For the nonrigid isometry, we focus on the general shape induced under loading conditions incompatible with the rigid mode. We show the response of the sample loaded and supported from opposite corners in Fig. 4(H). We see the type of shearing mode that is consistent with the mode shape shown in Fig. 2(D) based on our analytical calculations.

DISCUSSION

Our work develops analytical expressions for the large-scale low-energy deformations of rigidly foldable TBO and demonstrates the validity of our theory through experiment. We identify TBO as an architecture for control of shearing and breathing modes of surfaces through the geometry of the underlying crease pattern. Interestingly, we find the mountain/valley assignment controls the sign of the slope of the height-radius profile in the same way that the assignment controls the Poisson's ratio of parallelogram-based origami [34]. These results showcase new functionality for origami as mechanical metamaterials. Further development is required for the experimental demonstration of isometries in non-developable TBO, as well as the quantitative validation of the rigid isometry near the flattened state and the nonrigid isometry along the configuration manifold. We note that the nonrigid isometries of parallelogram-based origami still require the development of an experimental apparatus for their quantitative validation.

The theory developed in the present work connects the discrete representation to the continuum representation of locally uniform isometric deformations in TBO, thereby characterizing their low-energy kinematics at the large scale. It remains to test this theory with more general trapezoid crease patterns via analytical or numerical calculations. However, the underlying principles extend to quadrilateral-mesh origami sheets without parallel edges, where the breathing mode and the shearing mode are coupled along the configuration manifold, as well as axisymmetric origami such as those in Refs. [42–44], where the size of the faces changes between cells so

FIG. 4. Fabricated Miura-derivative trapezoid-based origami. (A) Fabricated tessellation with primitive lattice vectors $\ell_{1,2}$. (B) Primitive cell vertices labeled a, b, c , and d and faces labeled A, B, C , and D . (C) Sector angles labeled α and $\alpha' \equiv \pi - \alpha$ and dihedral angles labeled γ, ψ , and $\psi'' \equiv 2\pi - \psi$. (D) Compatibility diagram with amplitudes ν^a, ν^b, ν^c , and ν^d on the corresponding vertices and colors indicating the coupling coefficients $\zeta/q, -\xi/s$, and $+\xi/p$. (E) Edge lengths labeled p, q , and s . (F) View of folded specimen with height h , exterior radius R_e , and interior radius R_i with the mountain valley assignment of the folded creases indicated. (G) Radius as a function of height comparing experimental measurements with theoretical predictions. Black dashed line indicates flattened state. (H) Excitation of the non-rigid isometry. Scale bar is 30 mm in both panels (F) and (H).

454 that the continuum theory may adopt a conformally flat
 455 metric. Furthermore, our methods extend to spatially-
 456 varying isometries, such as those explored linearly for
 457 parallelogram-based origami [45, 46] (see Supplemental
 458 Appendix, Bloch-periodic Isometries) and nonlinearly for
 459 the cylindrical waterbomb origami [47], where the fun-
 460 damental forms and their derivatives are intimately re-

461 lated via the Gauss-Codazzi equations in the continuum
 462 regime [48].

463 In addition to characterizing the kinematics, quanti-
 464 fying the stiffness of the breathing and shearing modes
 465 is important for the application of our theory towards
 466 origami engineering. Such modal stiffness is frequently
 467 modeled via a truss model with Hookean potentials

FIG. 5. Rigid folding experiments of Miura-derivative trapezoid-based origami of the corresponding measurements shown in Fig. 4G with height h , inner radius R_i , and exterior radius R_e . The numbers correspond to those marked in Fig. 4(G)

468 for the folding, bending, and stretching of the pan- 480
 469 els [46, 49, 50]. In contrast to our theory, such truss
 470 models utilize virtual creases across the diagonals of the
 471 panels to quantify panel bending. Since our theory at-
 472 tempts to directly model the deflection field of the panels
 473 instead, it may be possible to equate the stiffness asso-
 474 ciated with the vertex amplitudes and the face ampli-
 475 tudes with scaling relations based on the dimensions of
 476 the panels and the elastic moduli of the constituent ma-
 477 terial. This could be especially valuable for the design of
 478 impact mitigating origami crash-boxes that utilize trape-
 479 zoidal faces [51].

METHODS

Coarse-Graining

482 We coarse-grain the ground states of a periodic origami
 483 tessellation by averaging its primitive lattice vectors over
 484 all admissible primitive unit cells to determine the coarse-
 485 grained tangent vectors of the tessellation. We do this in
 486 two steps. First, we average the lattice vectors over the
 487 copies of a standard unit cell that change which vertex
 488 is located at the origin and denote the result $\bar{\ell}_\mu$. For
 489 example, one copy has vertex a at the origin with lattice
 490 vectors pointing between vertex a in adjacent cells and

another copy has vertex b at the origin with lattice vectors pointing between vertex b in adjacent cells. Second, we average these copies between adjacent cells so that the forwards and backwards tangent vectors are equal and opposite. This yields our definition for the coarse-grained tangent vectors:

$$\mathbf{t}_\mu \equiv \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{S}^{-1})\bar{\ell}_\mu. \quad (11)$$

Additionally, we average the cell-to-cell change in the primitive lattice vectors over all admissible primitive unit cells to determine the change in the coarse-grained tangent vectors. We do this by averaging over the change in the tangent vector defined in Eqn. (11) from an initial cell to the subsequent cell and from the previous cell to the initial cell so that the forwards and backwards derivatives of the tangent vectors are equal and opposite. Since the change in the tangent vectors is given by the action of the lattice rotation matrix or its inverse, this yields our definition for the derivative of the coarse-grained tangent vectors:

$$\partial_\mu \mathbf{t}_\nu \equiv \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{S}_\nu - \mathbf{S}_\nu^{-1})\mathbf{t}_\mu. \quad (12)$$

These partial derivatives satisfy $\partial_\mu \mathbf{t}_\nu = \partial_\nu \mathbf{t}_\mu$. The indices of Eqns. (11, 12) remain the cell indices (n_1, n_2) . We transform to the continuous surface coordinates $(\hat{e}_1 = \varphi, \hat{e}_2 = z)$ via the Jacobian $J_{\mu\nu} = \partial \hat{e}_\mu / \partial n_\nu$. For the trapezoid-based origami crease patterns we consider, we have $J_{\varphi 1} = 1/\sin \eta$, $J_{z2} = 1/h$, and $J_{\varphi 2} = J_{z1} = 0$, where η is the lattice rotation angle and h is the magnitude of the second lattice vector.

We similarly coarse-grain the infinitesimal deformation of the periodic origami tessellation generated from a homogeneous isometry by averaging the corresponding lattice displacement $(\bar{\Delta}_\mu)$ and lattice angular velocity $(\bar{\mathbf{L}}_\mu)$ over all primitive unit cells. We again do this in two steps. First, we average the lattice displacement and lattice angular velocity over the same set of standard unit cells used to compute ℓ_μ above. Here, there are an additional four copies of each standard cell distinguished by the orientation of the frame for each of the four corners that meet at the vertex set at the origin. We denote the results $\bar{\Delta}_\mu$ and $\bar{\mathbf{L}}_\mu$. Second, we expand Eqns. (11, 12) in terms of these quantities:

$$\delta \mathbf{t}_\mu = \frac{1}{2}((\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{S}_\mu^{-1})\bar{\Delta}_\mu - \mathbf{S}_\mu^{-1}\bar{\mathbf{L}}_\mu\bar{\ell}_\mu), \quad (13)$$

$$\delta \partial_\mu \mathbf{t}_\nu = \frac{1}{2}((\mathbf{S}_\nu - \mathbf{S}_\nu^{-1})\delta \mathbf{t}_\mu + (\bar{\mathbf{L}}_\nu \mathbf{S}_\mu + \mathbf{S}_\mu^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{L}}_\nu)\bar{\ell}_\mu). \quad (14)$$

Again, the partial derivatives satisfy $\delta \partial_\mu \mathbf{t}_\nu = \delta \partial_\nu \mathbf{t}_\mu$ and we transform from the discrete cell indices to the continuous surface coordinates via the Jacobian. While

we do not compute an embedding directly, this procedure is sufficient to compute the fundamental forms and characterize the geometry of the origami tessellations. These methods extend to the crease patterns shown in Figs. 1(C,D) that are not periodic in the azimuthal direction but are still composed of cellular building blocks by performing the first step of our averaging between analogous, but nonequivalent, vertices in both the forward and backwards directions.

Linear Isometry Model

We model the linear isometries via the angular velocity field, denoted ω , which generates the infinitesimal rotation of elements of the sheet. We parameterize this angular velocity field via amplitudes on the vertices, denoted \mathcal{V}^a , and amplitudes on the faces, denoted \mathcal{F}^A , where we use lowercase (uppercase) Latin superscripts to label the vertex (face) within the primitive unit cell that the amplitude is assigned to. The meaning of the amplitudes is as follows. The difference in the angular velocity between the corners of two faces that meet at vertex a and share the i^{th} edge of the vertex is:

$$\Delta \omega = (-1)^i \mathcal{V}^a \zeta_i^a, \quad (15)$$

$$\zeta_i^a \equiv \hat{r}_{i+1}^a \times \hat{r}_{i+2}^a \cdot \hat{r}_{i+3}^a, \quad (16)$$

with i defined cyclically on the four edges emanating from vertex a and \hat{r}_i^a the corresponding edge direction. We refer to the triple products ζ_i^a as the triple products, which we can write explicitly as functions of the sector and dihedral angles. This local solution ensures that the net rotation around the vertex vanishes to first order in the angular velocity. Similarly, the difference in the angular velocity between the corners of face A that share the i^{th} edge of the face is:

$$\Delta \omega = (-1)^i \mathcal{F}^A \lambda_i^A, \quad (17)$$

$$\lambda_i^A \equiv \begin{cases} |\mathbf{r}_{i+2}^A|, & \text{parallel edges,} \\ |\mathbf{r}_i^A|, & \text{non-parallel edges} \end{cases}, \quad (18)$$

with i defined cyclically on the four edges bounding face A and $|\mathbf{r}_i^A|$ the corresponding edge length. This local solution ensures that the net rotation and displacement around the face vanishes to first order in the angular velocity.

We compute the net change in the orientation between any two corners of the origami tessellation by choosing a path composed of corner-to-corner segments and summing over the amplitude-dependent contributions to the angular velocity from Eqns. (15, 17). Similarly, we compute the net change in the position between any two corners by computing the change in the orientation between the starting corner and each corner along the path, then

576 summing each of their cross products with the subse-
 577 quent corner-to-corner segment along the path. The am-
 578 plitudes are constrained such that the total change in
 579 the angular velocity on a loop around any edge vanishes.
 580 These conditions ensure that both the net rotation and
 581 net displacement over any closed loop of the tessellation
 582 vanishes, and consequently that none of the elements of
 583 the sheet stretch to first order in the angular velocity. We
 584 provide a detailed derivation in Supplemental Appendix,
 585 Linear Isometry Compatibility Conditions.

586 Morph-derivative Trapezoid-based Origami 587 Geometry

588 We write the vertex basis vectors and the primitive
 589 lattice vectors for the family of Morph-derivative TBO
 590 with vertex a at the origin of the primitive unit cell as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_a &= (0, 0, 0), \\ \mathbf{r}_b &= (p, 0, 0), \\ \mathbf{r}_c &= (s_\alpha + q \cos \alpha, q \sin \alpha \cos \frac{\theta}{2}, q \sin \alpha \sin \frac{\theta}{2}), \\ \mathbf{r}_d &= (q \cos \alpha, q \sin \alpha \cos \frac{\theta}{2}, q \sin \alpha \sin \frac{\theta}{2}), \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ell_1 &= (p + s_\beta \cos \frac{\eta}{2}, s_\beta \sin \frac{\eta}{2}, 0), \\ \ell_2 &= \left(0, 0, \frac{2q \sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma}{\sin \frac{\eta}{2}}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

591 For all unit cells that appear in the averaging process,
 592 the lattice rotation angle is:

$$\eta = 2(\pi - \delta), \quad (21)$$

593 where we parameterize the dihedral angles entering
 594 Eqns. (19, 20, 21) through standard application of spher-
 595 ical geometry [52]:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta &= 2 \arctan \left(\frac{\cos \beta - \cos \alpha \cos \delta}{\sin \alpha \sin \delta}, \frac{\sin \beta \sin \gamma}{\sin \delta} \right), \\ \psi &= 2 \arctan \left(\frac{\cos \alpha - \cos \beta \cos \delta}{\sin \beta \sin \delta}, \frac{\sin \alpha \sin \gamma}{\sin \delta} \right), \\ \delta &\equiv \arccos(\cos \alpha \cos \beta + \sin \alpha \sin \beta \cos \gamma). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

596 Fabrication and Testing

597 We fabricate the Miura-derivative TBO by milling a 1
 598 mm thick black polypropylene sheet using a 3-axis CNC
 599 milling machine (Roland EGX-600, accuracy 10 μm),
 600 as illustrated in Fig. 6(A) and previously achieved in
 601 Refs [41, 53]. We form the mountain/valley creases by
 602 engraving 0.9 mm into the polypropylene sheet using a
 603 ball-end tool with a radius of 1 mm. To facilitate un-
 604 constrained folding, we add 2 mm diameter holes to each

605 vertex of the tessellation. This measure is crucial for pre-
 606 venting stress concentration where multiple creases con-
 607 verge, taking into account the non-zero thickness of the
 608 actual sample. Finally, since the Miura-derivative TBO
 609 is developable, we manually fold the milled/engraved
 610 polypropylene sheet.

611 We measure the height-radius profile along the non-
 612 linear rigid isometry of the fabricated Miura-derivative
 613 TBO using the experimental setup illustrated in
 614 Fig. 6(B,C). The setup consists of a linear slide system
 615 equipped with several sliders connected to an optical table
 616 and is arranged horizontally to mitigate gravitational
 617 effects. We connect the sample to a linear slide system
 618 via three sliders: one in the middle and the other two at
 619 its ends. Each slider is equipped with a locking system to
 620 maintain the sample at a fixed height. We affix PMMA
 621 spacers to the sliders using 2 mm diameter bolts, as illus-
 622 trated in Fig. 6(B), to ensure secure connection between
 623 the sample and the sliders. Additionally, we connect two
 624 L-shaped plates to extra sliders to induce the rigid fold-
 625 ing of the tessellation and establish the desired height
 626 for the sample. We design these plates to apply com-
 627 pression and tension to the sample, thereby facilitating
 628 both folding and unfolding.

629 We integrate two rulers into the setup: one to verify
 630 the imposed height of the sample and the other as a refer-
 631 ence scale bar for post-processing analysis of captured
 632 photos. We position two cameras, oriented orthogonal
 633 to one another, to capture images of the sample as we
 634 induce the rigid folding motion. We position the first
 635 camera (Sony Alpha 9) in front of the sample to cap-
 636 ture the frontal view, thereby facilitating the estimation
 637 of the radius. This camera is equipped with a telephoto
 638 G Master FE 100-400 mm lens to minimize distortion
 639 and enhance contrast between the foreground and the
 640 background. We position the second camera (Sony Al-
 641 pha 6300) to the side of the sample to capture the lateral
 642 view, thereby facilitating the estimation of the height.
 643 This camera is equipped with a Vario-Tessar T* FE 24-
 644 70 mm lens.

645 The experiments proceeded as follows. A specific
 646 height is imposed on the sample using the L-shaped
 647 plates and the sample is secured in this configuration
 648 by locking the sliders with the locking system. We use a
 649 tape measure at various positions along the circular edge
 650 of the tessellation to manually verify the uniformity of
 651 the sample height. We then capture a photo with each of
 652 the two cameras in the locked configuration. We repeat
 653 this process for eight different configurations, specifically
 654 imposing heights of 31.5 cm, 32 cm, 33 cm, 34 cm, 35
 655 cm, 36 cm, 37 cm, and 37.5 cm. Finally, we estimate
 656 the relationship between the height and radius via post-
 657 processing of these photos.

FIG. 6. (A) Manufacturing of trapezoid-based origami by a CNC milling machine. (B) Setup designed to perform the nonlinear rigid isometry experiments on the trapezoid-based origami. (C) Details of the setup showing the linear slide system used to change the configuration of the specimen during the experiments. The sample is constrained through multiple sliders inserted into a rail.

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